

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGY IN TEACHING SPECIAL SUBJECTS

Urakova Khabiba Bakhtyorovna

International University of Asia

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Abstract: Currently, special attention is paid to education and upbringing of young people. Education has always been the basis of society's development. Because a person is at the center of all relationships and connections in society. The revolution in science, technology and information makes a person and his scientific and educational potential a decisive factor of social and economic development.

Key words: Education, training, educational process, lesson, methodology, pedagogy, special subjects.

The process of qualitative improvement of economic growth factors is typical for the current stage of society's development. Application of the advanced results of scientific and technical development, intensification of production, along with the use of high-efficiency technical technologies, and most importantly, training of highly qualified specialists is one of the important directions in this regard. The problems of ensuring sustainable economic growth, taking a decent place in the international division of labor, and ensuring the competitiveness of the national economy largely depend on the knowledge, skills, and ability of the workforce to work depending on the situation. In order to achieve the great goals that we have to achieve in the future, first of all, we need to train highly qualified specialists who meet the requirements of the times. No matter what task we set in front of us, no matter what problem we need to solve, in the end it all comes down to personnel. It can be said without exaggeration that our future, the future of our country depends on who will replace us, or in other words, what kind of personnel will be trained.

As the entire education system is being reformed according to the Law on Education adopted in our country and the national program of personnel training that came into force in 1997, the main focus is on personnel training at this level. The importance of the education system in the upbringing of young people and their upbringing can be understood from the words of the President's greeting to the participants of the regional conference of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe "Education is an investment for the future": Deep understanding is important. Without creating an effective education system, it is difficult to imagine the implementation of the

tasks set for the reform of society. The priority given to this area is undoubtedly to prepare the ground for its future development.

The training of knowledgeable specialists and the development of human potential depend in every way on teachers, on their knowledge in organizing and teaching the teaching process. That is why special attention is being paid to the organization of the educational process and the use of educational methods that help students gain in-depth knowledge.

Organization of the educational process in the current period requires the teacher not only to have deep knowledge, but also to have pedagogical skills, to know various methods of teaching, and to work tirelessly on himself. As the basis of every person's life is economic activity, it is natural that every person is required to learn economic thinking. With the transition to a market economy, this demand has become stronger. In order for our children to be able to think economically from a young age, we began to study the basics of economic knowledge in our country starting from high school. The students of the higher education institution, especially of the educational institution of the economic direction, should be able not only to think economically, but also to identify and analyze a wide range of economic problems, to evaluate the trends of economic development, to feel how these changes can lead to future results. , it is necessary to learn to visualize. For this, deep knowledge of economic sciences is required. It is important to choose the right method for learning these subjects, which reflect the complex economic world. If the correct method is not chosen during the lesson, it will not give the expected result, regardless of the theoretical knowledge of the teacher. It is possible to effectively organize the educational process only when the teacher's knowledge is combined with pedagogical skills. For this, it is necessary to know various methods of organizing the educational process and their application. The teaching methodology (improvement) of special subjects is aimed at this very goal. Together with the term teaching method, the term teaching, teaching method is also often used.

The subject of the teaching methodology (success) is the teaching (teaching) process itself. The term "method" comes from the Greek word "methodos", which means research or way of knowing, theory, teaching. means name. Method means practical or theoretical methods of mastering reality. Scientific knowledge and its methods, covering the study of various aspects of activity, are the main direction of the methodology. In it, the methods of education and upbringing are in the main place. Usually, methodology (usuji) means the

science of a set of forms and methods of scientific knowledge activity. It is a set of methods or operations of learning, theoretical or practical knowledge of truth, reality, activity, to reach a theoretically set goal.

In pedagogical practice, according to tradition, a regulated method of activity used to achieve educational goals is understood as a method. It is emphasized that the methods of the teacher's teaching activity and the methods of the student's study activity are related to each other.

The teaching method is described as follows: the purpose of teaching, the method of learning, the interaction of the participants of the educational process (teacher, student).

Each special science studies its subject based on its general philosophical, general economic and other special features, using the methods specific to this science. In the process of studying science, not only the methods used in studying the subject of science, but also the methods used in organizing the process of learning and knowing the science are of great importance. Because in the process of education, bringing science to the minds of students, inviting them to learn, interest them, and directing them to work on themselves depends in many ways on the methods used in it.

The methodology of teaching special subjects is aimed at the formation of pedagogical thinking and thinking in students. On one side of the science of the teaching methodology of special subjects are scientific and philosophical sciences, and on the other side there are pedagogic sciences such as pedagogy, pedagogical technology, psychology. Special subjects, that is, the methodology of teaching special subjects, connects them together. Bachelors studying in the field of vocational education need to study pedagogy in depth.

The following tasks are assigned to the subject of teaching methodology of special subjects:

starting from economic subjects, to carry out continuous observation on the scale of the whole society, to bring to the minds of students how necessary it is to collect certain names and information;

- teaching students to process, compare, give comparative characteristics, and analyze economic information collected according to the set goal;
- in-depth study of events and processes, assessment of economic development trends and drawing conclusions;
- to be able to think economically, to think independently, to learn to justify one's point of view;
- to introduce teaching methods used for studying economic sciences;

- to be able to correctly connect teaching methods with the methods used in studying the subject of science;
- Knowing how to choose the teaching methods according to the subjects of science consists of learning how to use them skillfully in one's work.

In order for future specialists in the field of vocational education who have chosen the profession of pedagogue to meet the requirements set before them, in connection with the specialty subject:

- having a deep understanding of economic theory and other economic sciences;
- perfect knowledge of the sciences related to the construction of a legal state, a democratic society;
- striving to acquire pedagogical skills and experience to engage in youth education;
- to learn teaching methods well and be able to apply them according to the direction and topic of science;
- to know the history of the Uzbek people, to have national pride and culture;
- to be eager to learn news related to the specialty;
- to be interested in scientific and technical achievements;
- should be able to arouse interest in science based on the approved program for teaching science to students, should have the art of assigning tasks and demands according to the level and individual characteristics of each student

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